

THE ROLE OF RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article is about the Russian language and its role in the modern world, what is the Russian language and its meaning, the countries where Russian is spoken, the role of language on earth, the history of the Russian language.*

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Language is the most important means by which people communicate with each other. Russian is the national language of the Russian people. By its origin, the Russian language belongs to the Slavic languages. The closest Slavic languages to Russian are Ukrainian and Belarusian. It belongs to the state in the Russian Federation, and it is spoken by more than 500 million people around the world.

Not only in the CIS republics, but also in countries geographically far from the Russian Federation, there are strong communities speaking Russian: the USA, Turkey, Israel and others. Russian is one of the richest and most complex languages in the world. The peculiarity of the Russian language as a language of interethnic communication was manifested in the fact that it worked alongside and in parallel with them, performing its social functions. Reading, along with the native language, the Russian language is also important because it helps to exchange experiences and acquaint each nation and ethnic group with the cultural achievements of all other peoples and world culture. There is a constant process of mutual enrichment of the Russian language and the languages of the peoples of the world. Russian has been and remains one of the leading languages of the world. In the modern world, it ranks third in the number of Russian-speakers (500 million people) after the Chinese (over 1 billion) and the British (750 million). It is the official and working language in the most influential international organizations (UN, UNESCO, WHO, etc.).

Despite the existing problems, the situation has now somewhat stabilized. An increasing number of students choose Russian as a second foreign language. In particular, there is an increase in interest in mastering the Russian language among future economists, lawyers, doctors, and students of other educational programs. The Russian language is again becoming in demand by those who directly participate in the implementation of international projects, etc. Due to the growth of tourists from Russia, Russian language courses are being offered for service and hotel business workers. Anyway, the Russian language remains the language of interethnic communication throughout the post-Soviet space.

World languages are among the most common languages used by people of different nationalities outside the territories in which they originally lived. The functions of these languages cover international spheres — diplomacy, world trade, tourism. Scientists from different countries communicate with them. They are the "working languages" of the UN and other international

organizations and congresses, as well as "foreign languages", which are accepted as a subject of compulsory education in universities and schools in most countries of the world.

The composition of world languages is variable. Currently it includes English, Russian, French, Chinese and Arabic. The Russian language has long been a means of interethnic cooperation of many peoples and states. Since the middle of the 20th century, it has become a world language recognized throughout the world. Russian is associated with the richest Russian classical and modern fiction and is incomparable in the qualitative and quantitative translation of literature from all languages of the world into Russian. The acceptance of this language by humanity as a world language is connected with the prestige and place of this linguistic country in history and modernity.

In addition to socio-historical reasons, linguistic ones are also important... The question is to what extent this language is ready to teach speakers of other languages and cultures. It should be a national literary language with ancient written traditions, well-established norms, well-studied and described in grammars, dictionaries, textbooks. The Russian language has a very long and complex history of development. The oldest Russian literary language was formed in Kievan Rus and was the common language of the Eastern Slavs until the 14th century. In the 14th and 15th centuries, the Old Russian language was divided into three languages: Great Russian (Russian), Ukrainian and Belarusian.

Russian Russian, in other words, the Great Russian language began to develop on the territory of the Russian state, the center of which was Moscow. Russian dialects and dialects are divided into 2 groups: northern Velikorus ("hunter") and southern Velikorus ("hunter");

The Central Russian dialects reflect the peculiarities of both groups. In the 16th and 17th centuries, a kind of koine (common dialect) was formed in Moscow on the border of the northern and southern dialects, which became an exemplary language. Russian and the Russian national language emerged as significant differences between the literary language and the spoken language, which retained the features of Old Russian, and since the XVII century, the Russian nation and the Russian national language began to take shape. The literary language of the late 17th — early 18th centuries was rich and expressive, with

with many Western European accents, but was not stable. M. V. Lomonosov played an important role in its regulation and stabilization. At the beginning of the 19th century, the populism of the literary language was a big problem, and in solving this problem I.A. Krylov, A.S. Griboyedov, in particular, occupies a special place in the works of A. S. Pushkin. It is in Pushkin's work that the formation of the national Russian literary language ends. Pushkin's great merit is that in his work the national norms of the literary Russian language were developed and strengthened, and these norms were perceived by Pushkin's contemporaries and the next generation. The great representatives of Russian literature of the 19th and 20th centuries made a great contribution to the enrichment of the literary language; Since the second half of the XIX century, its development has been greatly influenced not only by writers, but also by public figures, scientists and cultural figures. After the October Revolution, due to the development of a special social system and science and technology, the Russian language, especially its vocabulary, underwent significant changes, the general democratization of the literary language intensified.

Unfortunately, the communicative method applied to the Russian language, which has a very complex prepositional and case-specific system, does not always bring the expected results. Therefore, methodological searches led to the need to include a new component in the term

"communicative competence". Language, or linguistic, competence has become such a component. The communicative component of modern teaching and upbringing methods is complemented by cognitive attitudes aimed at developing the thinking abilities of a foreign student and his behavior styles when mastering and assimilating Russian as a foreign language, which, in turn, implies not only the process of acquiring knowledge and experience, but also their use in educational and professional life. Russian is an inflexible synthetic language with 3 grammatical generic categories, 3 different types of nouns and 2 different types of verbs; Auxiliary words are put in the form of prepositions, that is, before the words with which they are associated.

Russian alphabet is based on Cyrillic alphabet (see Cyrillic alphabet) (see Russian alphabet). The highest thing that is written in it. the monuments date back to the XI century.

Since the middle of the 20th century, the study of the Russian language has become widespread all over the world. Russian is taught in more than 100 countries around the world. Russian Language and Literature Teachers International Association was established in 1967, and the Pushkin Institute of the Russian Language was founded in 1973. In Soviet times, special attention was paid to the teaching of the Russian language in Uzbekistan and a number of CIS countries, and even this process was carried out without fail. Even today, the teaching of the Russian language in our country, although not as mandatory as before, has not lost its significance.

From the standpoint of practical methodology, we consider it expedient to adhere to the following principles of teaching: - consciousness of learning consciousness of learning is realized primarily in the fact that students should intelligently perceive the theoretical facts of the language being studied, not only memorize, but also understand the rules of phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, word usage, work intensively and a lot on exercises that help them automate skills, and then consciously construct various statements first according to samples, and then on a given topic without relying on speech samples. A conscious approach to the formation of skills and abilities should permeate the entire learning process. As L.S. Vygotsky noted, the study of a foreign language "begins with awareness of the language and arbitrary mastery of it and ends with free spontaneous speech." Only conscious mastery of language material contributes to the formation of speech skills and abilities, activates the speech activity of students, makes the learning process communicative [Vygotsky 1996];

- the communicative nature of learning is the fundamental principle of modern methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language. The training is of a communicative nature if all the work is aimed at the formation of students' speech skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of speech activity – the process of communication. The communicative approach assumes not passive accumulation of knowledge about the language, but active mastery of language material, the ability to build their own utterance in the language being studied; - situational-thematic presentation of educational material to teach students to master the language practically, it is necessary to use such training techniques that would be close to the conditions of the real language environment; - functional approach to selection and submission language material assumes that all the facts of language should be considered from the point of view of their necessity for the expression of thought

- taking into account the specific conditions, goals and stages of learning, the presence or absence of a language environment significantly affects language learning and teaching methods. In the conditions of the language environment, the student hears Russian everywhere and is himself a faithful assistant in mastering the language. The lack of a language environment

complicates the learning process. Our task is to apply maximum effort to artificially create a language environment;

- using the native language of students rational use of the native language, on the one hand, helps to transfer knowledge, skills and abilities from the native language to the language being studied, and on the other hand, helps to overcome specific difficulties caused by the discrepancy between the native and the studied languages.

Working on Russian material that has an analogue in the native language of students, we note this similarity and give the necessary exercises. Considering the phenomena that are absent in the native language of students, we explain their meaning through the nearest equivalent and give a sufficient number of exercises.

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